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Ecosystem Restoration: The Bold Experiment for Rewilding Australia

UNITED NATIONS DECADE ON
**ECOSYSTEM
RESTORATION**
2021-2030

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As the United Nations launches its Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (2021-2030), it is timely to recall a champion for the cause with 'runs on the board'. His was a bold vision and the boldest of experiments in Australian conservation history. Exclude feral animals from Australian land and facilitate the recovery of the landscape to an ecologically balanced state. The feral-exclusion would be via feral-proof fences - steel mesh fencing high enough to stop ferals jumping over it, and buried deep enough to stop ferals burrowing under it. The key targets for exclusion were cats and foxes.

The grand experiment in rewilding Australia is told in a new book: ***A Vanishing Kind: A Memoir of Dr John Wamsley in Conversation*** (Wamsley & Davey, 2020). It is the story of the vision of John Wamsley, the man-in-the-cat-hat, and the publicly listed company he founded to reify his vision, Earth Sanctuaries Limited (ESL). The play out of the bold experiment is told irreverently and in a conversational style. The book is easy reading.

Dr John Wamsley bought an ex-dairy property at Mylor, on the outskirts of Adelaide, South Australia, in 1969. He set to work fencing it - with a feral-proof fence - and re-populating it with Australian native flora and fauna. Keep out cats

and foxes. It was a successful proof of concept - exclude the ferals and the natives could prosper. Warrawong Wildlife Sanctuary opened to the public in 1985.

The dual conservation and commercial successes of Warrawong, ushered in the temptation to replicate those successes, bigger and better. A new company, Earth Sanctuaries, was founded in 1988 with the view to develop further sanctuaries.

Earth Sanctuaries Limited (ESL) was floated on the Australian Stock Exchange (ASX) in 2000. The inflow of funds enabled the purchase of large tracts of land deemed suitable for sanctuaries, including in New South Wales and Victoria. So far so good.

An ambitious fencing plan was initiated, but fences are expensive, labour is expensive, fences need monitoring and maintenance, properties need managers, then factor in numerous obstacles and bureaucratic obstruction to be overcome. At its peak, ESL had 11 prospective sanctuaries, in 3 states, and accounted for 100,000 hectares.

Ultimately, it appears that Earth Sanctuaries failed for the lack of a viable business plan. Bureaucratic obstructionism didn't help. Wildlife were not 'stock', but could an accounting value be put on them? Apparently not. To attract paying customers and hence a cash flow, a sanctuary needed to be a going concern, with management, visitor facilities, visitor experiences, wildlife encounters, and be drivable from a population centre. Another 'cash cow', like Warrawong, never materialised in the brief history of Earth Sanctuaries. Management was passed from John Wamsley to his partner Proo Geddes, and then to an external CEO. In 2005, the company was delisted and wound up.

Since then, the mantra of John Wamsley has come in from the wilderness, and is now mainstream: "Feral cats threaten the survival of over 100 native species in Australia. They have caused the extinction of some ground-dwelling birds and small to medium-sized mammals. They are a major cause of decline for many land-based endangered animals such as the bilby, bandicoot, bettong and numbat. Many native animals are struggling to survive, so reducing the number killed by this introduced predator will allow their populations to grow" (DAWE, 2021).

It is estimated that, in a year in Australia, feral cats kill 596 million reptiles, 92 million frogs, 316 million birds, and 964 million mammals (Threatened Species Recovery Hub, 2019).

Earth Sanctuaries Limited (ESL) was the world's first publicly listed company whose business was conservation. The wonderful and curious platypuses and pademelons, bandicoots, bettongs and bridled nailtail wallabies, stick-nest rats,

woylies, bilbies, numbats, and so many others, were worth conserving, are still worth conserving. But how is it to be achieved?

Since Warrawong was relinquished by John Wamsley, the original sanctuary has changed ownership several times. It is once again in private hands (as of 2017), a going concern, and a wildlife sanctuary open to the public.

A charity, Australian Wildlife Conservancy (AWC), purchased some of the Earth Sanctuaries land out of bankruptcy. They state: "Australian Wildlife Conservancy is the largest private owner and manager of land for conservation in Australia, protecting endangered wildlife across more than 6.5 million hectares ... Recognising that 'business as usual' for conservation in Australia will mean additional extinctions, AWC is developing and implementing a new model for conservation" .

As has been observed, those who fail to learn from history are destined to repeat it. John Wamsley gave it his best shot, and he lives to tell the tale, frankly and fearlessly in this book, with sagacity, good humour, and with not too much bitterness.

The Wamsley vision was for 1% of Australia to be feral-free. What has been achieved to date is 0.1% (Threatened Species Recovery Hub, 2019). There remains much work to be done. How to avoid the 'tragedy of the commons' (Hardin, 1968) if the commons is no one's business? In contrast to a commercial enterprise, it remains an open question, how to fund an eco-enterprise?

Perhaps a lesson from the failure of Earth Sanctuaries and from the endurance of AWC since then, is that conservation is a charity not a business - at least for now. For those with a rewilding project or an ecosystem restoration plan in their sights, ***A Vanishing Kind*** is essential reading.

References

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A VANISHING KIND

A MEMOIR OF DR JOHN WAMSLEY
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